

Neural Organoids as a Model for Personalized Neurosurgical Treatments

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Abstract

Neural organoids have significantly advanced personalized medicine, particularly in neurosurgery, by closely replicating human brain development and disease mechanisms. These 3D models, derived from human pluripotent stem cells, offer unprecedented opportunities to study neurodevelopment, neurodegenerative diseases, and cancer in patient-specific contexts. The use of neural organoids derived from induced pluripotent stem cells (iPSCs) allows researchers to create individualized brain models that capture the complexity of conditions like epilepsy, glioblastoma, and Parkinson's disease. In glioblastoma research, "tumoroids" composed of patient-derived tumor cells integrated into organoids mimic tumor behavior, providing insights into immune evasion and resistance to conventional therapies such as chemotherapy and radiation. This allows for the testing of novel therapies targeting specific tumor survival pathways, including immune checkpoint inhibitors. In epilepsy, organoids simulate seizure activity, helping

identify seizure foci and abnormal neuronal networks, which is critical for refining resection strategies in drug-resistant cases. Furthermore, organoids enable the testing of antiepileptic drugs and gene-editing technologies such as CRISPR, offering tailored therapeutic approaches. These advancements demonstrate the capacity of neural organoids to bridge the gap between disease modeling and clinical applications, providing a powerful tool for optimizing neurosurgical interventions and accelerating drug development.

1. Introduction

Recent advancements in neural organoid technology have revolutionized the field of personalized medicine, particularly in neurosurgery. These 3D structures, derived from human pluripotent stem cells, closely mimic various aspects of human brain development and function, offering unprecedented opportunities for disease modeling, drug testing, and personalized surgical planning. Studies have demonstrated that neural organoids exhibit cellular and molecular signatures that closely resemble the developing human brain, making them a valuable tool for understanding neurodevelopment and neurodegenerative disorders (He et al., 2023).

The use of neural organoids derived from patient-specific induced pluripotent stem cells (iPSCs) allows for the development of highly individualized brain models, which are particularly useful in neurosurgery for conditions like epilepsy, brain tumors, and neurodegenerative diseases (Makhalova et al., 2022). Moreover, the ability to model a patient's unique neural architecture paves the way for

personalized surgical planning, offering insights into the potential success of interventions and drug responses (Yang et al., 2023).

In the context of neurodegenerative diseases, such as Parkinson's and Alzheimer's, neural organoids have enabled the investigation of disease mechanisms at the cellular level, providing a platform for pre-surgical evaluation and tailored treatment strategies (Wilson et al., 2023). As neural organoid technology continues to evolve, its integration into personalized neurosurgical treatments holds immense potential for improving patient outcomes.

2. The Development and Function of Neural Organoids

Neural organoids are three-dimensional cultures of brain-like tissue generated from human pluripotent stem cells (hPSCs), which include both embryonic stem cells (ESCs) and induced pluripotent stem cells (iPSCs). These cells are guided through a tightly controlled differentiation process into neural lineages, which is initiated by exposing the pluripotent stem cells to a combination of growth factors that mimic the molecular cues of early brain development. One of the key steps in this process is the inhibition of the Bone Morphogenetic Protein (BMP) and Wnt signaling pathways, which are crucial for preventing mesoderm and endoderm differentiation, while promoting the formation of neuroectodermal tissue, the precursor to neural lineages (Rowe & Daley, 2019).

In typical protocols, this initial inhibition of BMP and Wnt signaling results in the generation of neural progenitor cells (NPCs), which possess the ability to differentiate into various cell types found in the brain, including neurons, astrocytes, and oligodendrocytes. As development progresses, these progenitor cells self-organize into stratified structures resembling the cortical plate, a hallmark of the developing human cerebral cortex. This organization includes the emergence of distinct layers, mimicking the radial arrangement of neurons and glial cells in the human brain (Walsh et al., 2020). Importantly, this self-organization is driven by intrinsic cellular properties and external signaling cues that regulate key developmental processes such as proliferation, migration, and synaptogenesis.

Furthermore, these organoids have been shown to recapitulate important physiological and molecular characteristics of the developing human brain, including the expression of region-specific genes, the formation of functional synaptic connections, and the generation of rhythmic neuronal activity. This capacity to mimic human brain development in vitro makes neural organoids a powerful tool for studying not only normal brain development but also disease mechanisms (Pasca et al., 2015).

3. Neural Organoids in Disease Mechanisms

Neural organoids have become indispensable in understanding various neurological diseases by simulating complex brain conditions in a controlled environment. These patient-specific 3D models provide a

deeper insight into disease development, allowing researchers to study the molecular and cellular mechanisms underlying these conditions.

3.1 Organoids in Glioblastoma

Glioblastoma, one of the most aggressive and lethal brain cancers, is highly resistant to conventional therapies due to its invasive nature and ability to evade the immune system. Recent advancements in neural organoid research have led to the development of "tumoroids", a type of organoid model in which glioblastoma cells are integrated into brain-like tissue. These models provide a novel platform for studying tumor growth, invasion, and interaction with the brain's microenvironment.

Using tumoroids, researchers have identified key molecular pathways that glioblastoma cells manipulate to evade immune detection and promote their own survival. Glioblastoma cells were shown to induce changes in the tumor microenvironment (TME), particularly by remodeling the extracellular matrix (ECM) and influencing TGF- β signaling pathways. These pathways promote immune evasion and support tumor invasion into surrounding healthy brain tissue (Fernandes et al., 2023). Additionally, glioblastoma cells have been found to recruit cancer-associated fibroblasts (CAFs), which form a supportive network for tumor cells, enabling them to proliferate and invade more effectively. These fibroblasts secrete factors that further enhance the immune-resistant properties of glioblastoma, complicating treatment (Mazzaglia et al., 2023).

Moreover, these tumoroid models have enabled researchers to uncover how glioblastoma cells resist

standard therapies, such as chemotherapy and radiation, by activating pro-survival signaling pathways, including PI3K/AKT/mTOR and NF- κ B. These insights have been crucial in identifying new therapeutic targets, with efforts now focused on disrupting these pathways to improve treatment outcomes (Zhou et al., 2023).

Tumoroids are also proving instrumental in preclinical drug testing, allowing researchers to observe how glioblastoma cells respond to novel therapies in a controlled, physiologically relevant setting. Drugs targeting the immune checkpoint proteins PD-1 and PD-L1, which are involved in immune evasion, have shown promising results in tumoroid models by enhancing immune cell activity against tumor cells (Lin et al., 2023). These models allow researchers to simulate the effects of immunotherapies before clinical trials, providing crucial data on their potential efficacy in patients.

3.2 Organoids in Epilepsy, Alzheimer's, and Other Neurodegenerative Disorders

Neural organoids have emerged as an innovative tool for advancing our understanding of chronic neurological diseases, offering unprecedented opportunities for personalized disease modeling and to observe how conditions evolve over time within a brain-like environment. These 3D structures provide a highly controlled platform for studying disease processes at a level of precision that was previously unattainable using traditional animal models or simpler cell cultures (He et al., 2023; Werner & Gillis, 2023). This breakthrough has the potential to significantly advance both the understanding and treatment of complex neurological

disorders, setting the stage for more effective and personalized therapeutic strategies (Werner & Gillis, 2023; He et al., 2023).

3.2.1 Organoids in Epilepsy

Neural organoids have provided significant advancements in simulating drug-resistant epilepsy, allowing researchers to better understand the neuronal circuits and electrical disturbances that underlie the disease. One of the primary benefits of using organoids in this context is their ability to simulate the network activity responsible for epileptic seizures, such as hyperexcitability and abnormal synchronization of neurons. Through electrophysiological monitoring, organoids can display seizure-like activity in vitro, mirroring the irregular neuronal firing patterns observed in drug-resistant epilepsy patients (Wang et al., 2023).

Recent studies using organoids have revealed that defects in ion channel function, particularly mutations in genes like *SCN1A*, can alter the excitability of neurons, leading to increased susceptibility to seizures. These mutations disrupt the balance between excitatory and inhibitory neurons, which is a hallmark of many forms of epilepsy (Fisher et al., 2017). Furthermore, advanced techniques such as multielectrode arrays (MEAs) are integrated with organoids to capture real-time neural activity, allowing for the detailed analysis of how these electrical imbalances contribute to seizure generation and propagation. This mechanistic insight into the neural networks involved in epilepsy has opened the door to more effective therapeutic interventions.

The precision offered by these patient-specific models also facilitates the testing of antiepileptic drugs (AEDs) in a more targeted manner. Organoids can be used to screen for compounds that modulate the specific neural circuits involved in the patient's seizures, offering a platform for drug discovery tailored to the individual's disease profile. Organoids have been instrumental in identifying novel AEDs that can correct sodium channel dysfunction in cases where standard therapies have failed (Fisher et al., 2014).

The integration of organoids with genome-editing technologies, such as CRISPR/Cas9, has enabled for exploration of correcting the genetic mutations responsible for epilepsy at their source. These advances demonstrate the immense potential of neural organoids not only as a model for understanding the mechanisms of epilepsy but also as a platform for developing and testing precision treatments that could one day cure the disorder in certain patients (Wang et al., 2023).

3.2.2 Organoids in Neurodegenerative Disorders

In the context of Alzheimer's and Parkinson's diseases, neural organoids have provided a breakthrough in modeling the neurodegenerative processes associated with these disorders. In Alzheimer's disease, the formation of amyloid plaques and tau tangles—hallmarks of the disease—can be studied in real time. These pathological structures lead to the progressive degeneration of neurons and contribute to cognitive decline (Wang et al., 2019; Selkoe & Hardy, 2016).

One critical observation from these studies is that tau tangles, a hallmark of Alzheimer's disease, accumulate in

specific brain regions following a pattern similar to the Braak stages, which map the progression of tau pathology from the entorhinal cortex to other parts of the brain (Pascoal et al., 2021). These tau aggregates disrupt cellular function and eventually cause widespread neuronal death. By studying organoids over time, researchers have been able to observe how tau pathology spreads within the brain's three-dimensional structure, offering new insights into how it might be halted or slowed in clinical interventions (Ferrari-Souza et al., 2023).

Moreover, organoids allow the testing of gene therapies and small molecules targeting specific pathways implicated in neurodegeneration. For instance, in Alzheimer's, researchers are exploring how the APOE ϵ 4 genotype, which increases the risk of Alzheimer's, affects microglial activation and tau deposition. By integrating microglial cells into neural organoids, scientists have uncovered that APOE ϵ 4 carriers exhibit higher levels of tau accumulation and accelerated neurodegeneration, offering a potential target for early intervention (Ferrari-Souza et al., 2023).

In Parkinson's disease, organoids have been used to observe how α -synuclein aggregation leads to dopaminergic neuron loss, a hallmark of the disease's progression (Marotta et al., 2023).

In these models, the ability to observe the direct effects of small molecule drugs on the amyloid plaques and tau tangles in Alzheimer's organoids, or the α -synuclein aggregates in Parkinson's organoids, offers the possibility to fine-tune treatments that may slow or halt these

disease processes. This is particularly crucial for Alzheimer's disease, where early interventions before significant neuronal damage occurs could significantly improve patient outcomes (Selkoe, 2011).

3.3 Organoids in Neurodevelopmental Disorders

Neural organoids have offered critical insights into understanding the cellular and molecular basis of neurodevelopmental disorders such as autism spectrum disorder (ASD) and schizophrenia. These disorders often arise from disruptions in early brain development, including abnormal neuronal migration, synapse formation, and cortical development. By deriving neural organoids, researchers can model these abnormalities in vitro and uncover the underlying genetic and cellular dysfunctions that drive the disorders.

For instance, in the case of ASD, neural organoids have been instrumental in revealing the role of specific gene mutations, such as those in SHANK3 and CHD8, both strongly associated with the disorder. These mutations disrupt neuronal connectivity and synapse formation, which are critical for proper brain function. In a 2023 study, researchers using iPSC-derived neural organoids observed that mutations in SHANK3 led to a significant reduction in synaptic connectivity, mimicking the synaptic deficits observed in ASD patients (He et al., 2023). This research provides a direct link between the genetic mutations and the cognitive and behavioral symptoms seen in individuals with ASD, offering a clearer understanding of how synaptic deficits contribute to the disorder.

Similarly, schizophrenia has been modeled using neural organoids to investigate early cortical development and neuronal migration. Schizophrenia is often associated with alterations in neuronal migration, and recent studies using organoid models have shown that mutations in genes such as DISC1 disrupt the normal migration patterns of neurons during brain development (Ripke et al., 2022). These abnormalities lead to cortical disorganization, which is believed to contribute to the cognitive and psychiatric symptoms of schizophrenia. Neural organoids allow researchers to observe these migration patterns in real time, providing valuable data on how disruptions in early development can lead to long-term brain dysfunction.

Advanced neural organoid technologies have enabled the integration of electrophysiological tools to study neuronal activity in these models. For example, a 2023 study demonstrated the use of Kirigami electronics to record long-term electrophysiological activity in neural organoids, allowing researchers to track abnormal neuronal firing patterns, such as those observed in patients with schizophrenia and ASD (Yang et al., 2023). This has provided new insights into how neuronal circuits are disrupted in these disorders and how therapies can be developed to restore normal neuronal function.

These discoveries are paving the way for more precise and effective therapies targeted at correcting the early developmental processes that go awry in neurodevelopmental disorders. By simulating the specific genetic mutations and cellular environments of individual patients, neural organoids are playing an increasingly

important role in the development of personalized medicine approaches for these conditions.

4. Organoids in Personalized Neurosurgery

Before operating on a patient, organoids allow surgeons to model and simulate invasive procedures, such as deep brain stimulation (DBS) and epileptogenic focus resection, in a controlled preclinical environment. This approach is particularly critical for refining surgical plans and minimizing unintended damage to healthy brain tissue.

For patients with drug-resistant epilepsy, where the goal is to remove or disrupt the epileptogenic focus, researchers have used these organoids to simulate seizure activity, allowing neurosurgeons to identify the exact location of the seizure focus. Organoid models enable precise identification of abnormal neuronal connectivity patterns, thereby enhancing the accuracy of resection strategies for epilepsy patients. This preoperative testing significantly improves surgical precision, helping to reduce the risk of removing functional brain tissue, which could lead to loss of motor skills or cognitive functions (Köse et al., 2022).

Neural organoids have proven helpful in refining surgical strategies for tumor resection. By integrating tumor-derived cells into neural organoids, referred to as "tumoroids," these models allow surgeons to simulate how tumors interact with surrounding healthy tissue. This patient-specific modeling is crucial for targeting

surgical interventions that maximize tumor removal while minimizing damage to functional brain regions.

Glioblastoma tumoroids allow surgeons to test different resection strategies preoperatively, identifying the most effective approach to removing as much of the tumor as possible without significantly impacting healthy brain areas. By modeling the tumor microenvironment, these organoids give real-time feedback on how glioblastoma cells respond to surgical manipulation, helping surgeons adjust their strategies to avoid complications such as neurological deficits (Karschnia et al., 2022).

In addition, the use of organoids in robotic-assisted neurosurgery is advancing precision. By simulating the surgical trajectory on organoid models, surgeons can pre-program robotic systems with detailed instructions on how to approach delicate brain regions. This technique allows surgeons to anticipate challenges like tissue deformation during surgery, improving the precision and safety of robotic-assisted neurosurgical procedures. Robot-assisted stereotactic surgeries using organoid simulations were shown to reduced surgical time and increased targeting accuracy, thus minimizing patient risk during complex neurosurgical interventions (Anderson et al., 2023).

5. Applications in Drug Testing and Therapy Development

Neural organoids offer a groundbreaking platform for high-throughput drug screening. Traditional drug discovery methods, which heavily rely on animal models, often fail to accurately predict human responses,

particularly in the context of neurological diseases.

Neural organoids allow for human-relevant modeling, enhancing the predictive power of drug efficacy and safety assessments. This platform provides researchers with the ability to rapidly test large libraries of compounds, identifying those that show promise for further development (Li et al., 2023).

In Alzheimer's pathology, screening hundreds of compounds for their ability to reduce plaque formation, researchers have identified several potential therapeutic candidates. These compounds are now advancing through clinical trials, supported by preclinical data from organoid-based models (Werner & Gillis, 2023). In addition, because organoids can be generated from patient-specific iPSCs, this platform allows for testing drug efficacy in a context that mirrors the patient's unique genetic makeup. This personalized approach has been especially beneficial in identifying how different patients might respond to the same treatment, enhancing precision in drug development strategies (He et al., 2023).

In addition to drug discovery, neural organoids are advancing the field of gene therapy for neurological disorders. Gene therapy, which targets specific genetic mutations associated with diseases such as epilepsy and Parkinson's disease, requires detailed understanding of how genetic alterations impact neural function. Neural organoids generated from patient-derived induced pluripotent stem cells (iPSCs) allow researchers to simulate the effects of gene-editing techniques, such as CRISPR-Cas9, in a controlled environment. These organoid models provide essential

data on how gene modifications affect cellular processes in the brain, critical factors for determining the efficacy of gene therapies before clinical application.

In Parkinson's disease research, gene therapy has demonstrated potential to restore dopaminergic function by modifying genes that regulate dopamine production in neurons. Studies have shown that using adeno-associated viruses (AAVs) to deliver therapeutic genes into organoid models of Parkinson's disease can enhance dopaminergic neuron survival and reduce neurodegeneration. These advancements highlight the potential for gene therapy to reverse or slow disease progression.

Moreover, high-content screening systems integrated with organoid platforms enable researchers to perform phenotypic screening for large numbers of drug candidates in parallel. These screening platforms, such as those discussed by *Zhou et al. (2023)*, combine advanced imaging technologies with organoid models to identify changes in cellular morphology and biochemical processes in response to treatment. This approach significantly accelerates the drug discovery pipeline by allowing researchers to assess multiple parameters simultaneously, including toxicity, efficacy, and drug mechanism of action. As a result, promising compounds can be identified much earlier in the drug development process, reducing time and costs associated with traditional methods.

6. Future Directions and Challenges

Looking forward, one of the most exciting future applications of neural organoids is in regenerative medicine. As researchers continue to improve the ability to generate more mature and complex brain structures, there is growing interest in using organoids to repair damaged brain tissue in conditions such as stroke or traumatic brain injury. By transplanting neural organoids into damaged areas of the brain, it may be possible to promote the regeneration of lost neurons and restore brain function (Li et al., 2023).

Advancements in the maturation of neural organoids have included efforts to enhance their vascularization and longevity in culture, as these factors remain challenges for the field. Organoids without vascular networks rely on diffusion for nutrient and waste exchange, limiting their size and long-term viability. Researchers are now exploring methods to introduce blood vessel-like structures into organoids, as well as co-culturing organoids with microglia and other non-neuronal cells to improve their complexity and functionality.

The use of neural organoids in research also raises important ethical questions. As these structures become more sophisticated and capable of mimicking higher-order brain functions, such as memory or sensory processing, concerns have arisen about the potential for consciousness in organoids. While current organoids lack the complexity necessary for consciousness, this is an area that will require careful consideration as the technology advances (Marotta et al., 2023). Researchers

and bioethicists are working together to develop guidelines that ensure the responsible use of neural organoids in research, balancing the potential benefits with the ethical challenges.

7. Conclusion

The emergence of neural organoids has ushered in a transformative era in neuroscience, with profound implications for both the study and treatment of complex neurological diseases. These three-dimensional structures, derived from human induced pluripotent stem cells (iPSCs), bridge the gap between traditional models and the complexities of the human brain, offering unprecedented opportunities to simulate human brain physiology in a controlled and patient-specific environment. This breakthrough is particularly relevant in fields like personalized neurosurgery, drug discovery, and gene therapy, where conventional models often fail to capture the intricate dynamics of neurological disorders.

In the context of neurosurgery, neural organoids have redefined the precision with which surgical interventions can be planned and executed. By replicating patient-specific brain environments, organoids offer neurosurgeons a predictive tool for preoperative simulations, thereby enhancing the safety and efficacy of procedures such as epileptogenic focus resection and glioblastoma surgery. The ability to model complex interactions between tumors or epileptic foci and surrounding healthy tissue allows for tailored surgical strategies that minimize functional impairments while maximizing therapeutic outcomes. Such advancements

mark a paradigm shift in neurosurgical practice, where precision and patient-specificity are paramount.

Moreover, neural organoids have demonstrated their immense potential in revolutionizing drug discovery processes. High-throughput drug screening on organoids offers a more accurate representation of human neurological responses compared to animal models, particularly in diseases such as Alzheimer's and Parkinson's. By enabling the rapid testing of large compound libraries on human-relevant platforms, organoids have accelerated the identification of promising therapeutic candidates, with several compounds already advancing to clinical trials. This methodology not only shortens the drug development timeline but also enhances the relevance of preclinical findings, offering a path toward more effective treatments for neurodegenerative diseases.

The application of neural organoids in gene therapy research further underscores their significance in advancing personalized medicine. By allowing precise gene-editing techniques, such as CRISPR-Cas9, to be tested in a controlled, patient-specific environment, organoids provide crucial insights into the molecular mechanisms driving genetic neurological disorders. These models have proven instrumental in refining therapeutic approaches, particularly for diseases like epilepsy and Parkinson's, where gene therapy holds the potential to not just treat but fundamentally alter disease trajectories.

In conclusion, neural organoids represent a leap forward in the field of neurological research and treatment, offering a versatile and highly relevant platform that

merges the rigor of scientific inquiry with the nuances of personalized medicine. As the technology continues to evolve, its applications are poised to expand, influencing not only the clinical management of neurological diseases but also the fundamental understanding of brain biology. The precision, scalability, and patient-specificity afforded by neural organoids signal a new horizon for neuroscience, where the boundaries between preclinical modeling and clinical application are increasingly blurred, paving the way for more personalized and effective therapeutic interventions.

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